

Application of Automated Floating Chamber to Quantify CO₂ and CH₄ Fluxes from Inland Freshwater Systems in Sri Lanka

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Introduction

Tropical freshwater systems are significant sources of greenhouse gases, particularly carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄). However, estimation of their contributions to global carbon budgets remain uncertain (Canadell et al. 2021). Further, these systems are characterized by their unique climatic and ecological conditions. In Sri Lanka, where numerous tropical freshwater systems exist, data on CO₂ and CH₄ emissions are lacking. Accurate and cost-effective monitoring and estimations of these fluxes are important for better understanding of the emission dynamics and introducing climate-related policies.

Floating chamber methods are widely adopted globally for measuring gas fluxes, and recent advancements in low-cost sensor technologies offer new opportunities for real-time, high resolution monitoring in resource-limited settings (Bastviken et al. 2020). There is no published literature on application of floating chamber method to quantify carbon flux from freshwater systems of Sri Lanka. This study aimed to build an automated floating chamber from locally available materials and quantify carbon flux from inland freshwater systems.

Methodology

An automated floating chamber was developed and deployed to quantify CO₂ and CH₄ emissions from three permanently flooded, man-made freshwater systems in Sri Lanka: Thalangama Lake, Kandy Lake, and Hurulu Wewa. Field deployments were conducted at Thalangama Lake on 5th March 2025, Kandy Lake on 11th March 2025, and Hurulu Wewa on 25th March 2025.

The chamber, having dimensions of 0.30 m in width, height, and length, was constructed using transparent acrylic sheets and mounted on a Styrofoam base with dimensions of 0.91 m in length, 0.60 m in width, and 0.0635 m in height to ensure buoyancy. To minimize the influence of external temperature, the chamber was insulated using aluminum double bubble wrap. The bottom opening of the chamber, which was in contact with the water surface, had an area of 0.0625 m².

For measurements of gas concentration, an MQ4 semiconductor sensor (Winson Electronics) was used for CH₄ detection, and a Non-Dispersive Infrared (NDIR) sensor (SCD30, Sensirion Holding) was used for CO₂. These sensors tested for field application without further improvement. (Furuta et al. 2022; Mitchell et al. 2024) Both sensors were calibrated in well aerated ambient air, assuming baseline concentrations of 1.9 ppm for CH₄ and 421 ppm for CO₂ (Bastviken et al. 2020).

A DHT22 sensor was used to measure air temperature and relative humidity, while an RTC3231 module provided accurate timekeeping. All sensors were strategically mounted at the 0.05 m below from top panel of the chamber to ensure uniform exposure and minimize potential measurement biases. No active mixing was incorporated inside the chamber to avoid disturbing the natural water-air interface, following standard practice in passive flux measurements where gas accumulation is driven by natural convection and diffusion. An Arduino Uno microcontroller processed the sensor outputs and logged the data onto an SD card in every 2 seconds. Gas accumulation and flushing were controlled using an R365 diaphragm-based air pump, operated via a Delay Trigger Module (JZ-801).

Fluxes were measured at hourly intervals. Each cycle included a 40-minute gas accumulation period inside the sealed chamber, followed by a 20-minute flushing period to reset the internal air. This automated process allowed for continuous, unattended data collection in the field. Five-hour fluxes were quantified in each lake during March 2025. The total dissolved solids (TDS), pH, Electric conductivity (EC), Dissolved oxygen, Temperature, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), Atmospheric pressure and Salinity were recorded using Hanna HI9829 Multiparameter. Incoming solar power was logged with TES1333R solar power meter.

Then gas fluxes were calculated using the Equation 1,

$$F = \frac{V}{RTA} \times \frac{dC}{dt} \times 3600 \dots\dots\dots (Eq 1)$$

Where F = Flux of the specific gas ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$), $\frac{dC}{dt}$ = Concentration changes over the time ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$), T = ambient temperature (K), R = Universal gas constant ($\text{m}^3 \text{atm K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$), A = Chamber area in contact with water (m^2), V = Chamber volume (m^3)

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the diffusive fluxes of CO₂ and CH₄ with time in all 3 locations studied. These measurements demonstrated that the automated floating chamber was capable of quantifying both diffusive fluxes of CO₂ and CH₄, as well as ebullitive fluxes of CH₄ from freshwater systems. The results revealed considerable spatial variability in flux rates across the three study sites. Among the quantified hourly diffusive CH₄ fluxes, the highest and lowest values were recorded at Kandy Lake, with rates of $62.43 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$

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and 11.10 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively. Notably, ebullitive CH₄ events were observed only at Kandy Lake, with fluxes of 1455.83 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and 634.33 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$.

Table 1. Diffusive CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes

Time	Kandy Lake $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{hr}$	Thalangama Lake $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{hr}$	Hurulu wewa $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{hr}$
Diffusive CO ₂ fluxes			
10:00 AM	1,716.97	5,860.43	N/A
11:00 AM	506.9	1,772.13	554.9
12:00 PM	1,230.21	1,524.85	114.78
13:00 PM	676.94	2,285.46	139.51
14:00 PM	139.27	371.20	594.15
15:00 PM	N/A	N/A	569.21
Diffusive CH ₄ fluxes			
10:00 AM	13.43	36.51	N/A
11:00 AM	11.1	24.64	58.22
12:00 PM	62.43	25.05	43.92
13:00 PM	20.4	22.29	31.75
14:00 PM	40.14	36.29	22.17
15:00 PM	N/A	N/A	25.12

N/A=Not available

The highest CO₂ flux recorded at Thalangama Lake (5860.43 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{hr}$) while lowest value showed by the Hurulu wewa (114.78 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{hr}$). The variation of carbon fluxes may depend environmental and anthropogenic factors. Figure 1 illustrates the CH₄ flux with solar energy at Kandy Lake. Water quality parameters in each lake were shown in Table 2.

Figure 1. CH₄ flux and Solar energy variation of Kandy Lake

Table 2. Water quality parameters of each lake

Parameter	Kandy Lake	Thalangama Lake	Huruluwewa
pH	7.60	7.36	8.36
Total dissolved solids (TDS) (mg/L)	155	102	156
EC (μS)	311	204	312
Mean Water Temperature (°C)	27.43	30.85	32.39
Oxidation-reduction potential (ORP) (mV)	-22.0	-26.5	-16.8
Salinity (PSU)	0.15	0.09	0.15

The CH₄ fluxes show a positive correlation with Solar Energy, Air temperature, Water temperature and wind speed. Extensive field measurements are needed to identify exact influencing factors on CH₄ and CO₂ fluxes that specific to the Sri Lankan Environment.

These results identify significant spatial variability in greenhouse gas emissions, potentially influenced by environmental and anthropogenic factors.

Conclusion

The successful deployment of this automated floating chamber demonstrates its feasibility for long-term, high-resolution flux monitoring in tropical freshwater systems in Sri Lanka. This system could play an important role in freshwater ecosystem carbon assessments, contributing to climate change mitigation strategies and greenhouse gas reporting.

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